

STUDY AND CONTROL OF MATRIX CONVERTER BASED PMSG SYSTEMS IN WIND POWER GENERATION

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Abstract:

Combining a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) with a direct AC-AC matrix converter enables the production of utility-scale wind energy. This study primarily focuses on the control aspects of a variable-speed wind turbine utilizing a PMSG-based design with adjusted pitch angles and a control method. The matrix converter plays a pivotal role in facilitating the connection of the generator to the grid. It efficiently converts the high-frequency output generated by the turbine into the standard frequency required by the utility system using a switching technique. Power and voltage within the matrix converter are managed by a PI controller. MATLAB/Simulink simulations validate the anticipated system performance, highlighting the indispensable role of matrix converters.

Keywords - Wind Turbine, PMSG, Matrix Converter, Proportional-Integral (PI) Control, Pulse Width Modulation (PWM).

1. Introduction

Electricity is produced from renewable resources like the sun and wind. Variable wind turbines can produce electricity in a variety of wind conditions. A wind turbine transforms mechanical energy into electrical energy and relies on renewable energy sources. A Matrix Converter that is directly connected to the grid is attached to a PMSG, it accommodates a wind turbine. Depending on the wind speed, tip speed ratio, and pitch angle, the wind turbine's output, speed, and torque operate the PMSG. Without a pitch angle It is impossible to regulate the speed of a wind turbine. When the hybrid energy of wind speed reaches a specified threshold, the turbine will automatically shut off. Otherwise, the PMSG will lose control over its speed and cause the system to sustain numerous damages. A three-phase utility power with lower harmonics was produced by integrating a three-phase matrix converter and a variable-speed PMSG. The operation of the matrix converter in conjunction with the PMSG is modeled using the machine's voltage and current equations. There is no some other need for a Direct Current link energy storage component because the converter of the matrix is a single-stage converter. To achieve sinusoidal input and output voltage and current waveforms for

an AC/AC matrix converter, various switching sequences have been used. The development and investigation of a control approach focused on Altering the on-off time ratio of the Utilizing a matrix converter for the purpose of regulating power injection into the grid. The matrix converter operates using some Methods for modulating pulse widths to enhance the efficiency of Optimal voltage transfer. The output of the matrix converter is sent to a grid that needs changeable voltage and variable frequencies, such as one that powers PMSG. The design and construction of a 3-phase matrix converter for wind energy conversion involves the implementation of a control strategy. A wind system with PMSG represented in a MATLAB/Simulink file is used to interpret the simulation results of control approaches.

2. Literature Survey

Guoliang Yang et al [1] discussed in the Nine bidirectional switches are matrix converter designed to transform a low frequency three-phase input into a high frequency one-phase output. Benefits include the ability to operate over a wide input voltage range, low total harmonic distortion in line current, high efficiency, parallel operation capability, and incorporated closed loop control.

In [2], MA Xing-he examined commutation switching sequences in a matrix converter, comparing it to an AC-DC-AC converter. Unlike the latter, the matrix converter lacks built-in freewheeling paths. The research delved into commutation process mechanisms and explored methods to enhance it, including adjusting switching sequences and commutation times based on the synthesis of two line voltages.

In the work of Bekhada Hamane [3], a flux-oriented control strategy is proposed to manage current and power. This control approach integrates a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller, the pole placement technique,

and the Venturini Modulation Method (VMM) to oversee the functionality of the matrix converter. The efficiency and reliability of this wind energy conversion system are confirmed through an evaluation of its performance in both transient and steady-state conditions.

Quoc-Hoan Tran [4] introduced a practical alternative to the standard six-leg indirect matrix converter by developing a five-leg indirect matrix converter and incorporating space vector modulation. This cost-effective setup aims to efficiently supply power to a three-phase open-end load. It cleverly combines a single inverter leg with two load terminals, reducing the reliance on power switches. By utilizing pulse-width modulation, the proposed drive system excels in generating a line-to-line output voltage and achieves an improved voltage transfer ratio of up to 1.5.

3. Modelling of Wind Turbine

Wind turbines, employing Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generators (PMSG), convert the mechanical energy from the wind into electrical energy. Figure 1 depicts the block diagram of the proposed model.

Fig 1: Block diagram of the proposed system

The formula for wind power calculation is given as,

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} * C_p(\lambda, \beta) * \rho * v^3 * A \quad (1)$$

Where A represents the rotor area of the turbine, it signifies the tip speed ratio, and denotes the rotor pitch angle. In this equation, C_p stands for the power coefficient, Kg/m^3

represents air density, V indicates wind speed in m/s, while the remaining variables are C_p , and v .

The mathematical expression representing the power coefficient is as follows:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = C_1 \left(\frac{C_2}{\lambda_i} - C_3 * \beta - C_4 * \beta - C_5 \right) e^{\frac{C_6}{\lambda_i}} \quad (2)$$

The constants, $C_1=0.5$, $C_2=116$, $C_3=0.4$, $C_4=0$, $C_5=21$, and $C_6=0.0068$ hold the following values. The highest values of C_p were achieved when $i=0$ and $i=8.1$.

The formula representing mechanical torque is provided as follows :

$$T_m = \frac{P_m}{w} \quad (3)$$

Where, P_m represents the mechanical output power, w is the turbine rotor speed and T_m stands for the mechanical torque.

4. Modelling of drive train

The wind turbine's drive train is considered its mechanical system, comprising both the generator and the turbine. Its primary function is to transform the slower generator turbine speed into the desired wind turbine speed.

The following equation relates to the driving train:

$$2H_t \frac{dw_t}{dt} = T_m - T_s \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{1}{w_{ebs}} \frac{d\theta_{sta}}{dt} = w_t - w_r \quad (5)$$

Where, H_t denotes the inertia constant of the turbine, θ_{sta} represents the shaft twist angle, w_t stands for the angular speed of the wind turbine, w_r signifies the rotor speed of the generator, w_{ebs} is the Electrical base speed, T_s represents the shaft torque.

5. Modelling of PMSG

Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generators (PMSG) are utilized in synchronous machines that lack field windings and have a simple rotor design. Here is a

potential representation for the voltage equations of PMSG:

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_d = \frac{1}{L_d} v_d - \frac{R}{L_d} i_d + \frac{L_q}{L_d} p w_r i_q \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_q = \frac{1}{L_q} v_q - \frac{R}{L_q} i_q - \frac{L_d}{L_q} p w_r i_d - \frac{\lambda p w_r}{L_q} \quad (7)$$

In this context, where i_d and i_q represent the currents along the d_q axis, R stands for the stator winding resistance, L_d and L_q denote the inductance along the d_q axis, v_d and v_q are the voltages along the d_q axis, and w_r represents the rotor's rotational speed.

The formula for calculating the electromagnetic torque can be expressed as,

$$T_e = 1.5p[\lambda i_q + (L_d + L_q)i_d i_q] \quad (8)$$

where represents the amplitude of the generated flux, and p indicates the number of pole pairs.

6. Matrix Converter Modeling

The matrix converter can be depicted with nine bidirectional switches, each identified as S_{ij} ,

where $i = \{A, B, C\}$ and $j = \{a, b, c\}$ correspond to the output voltage indices.

When the switches are in the "closed" state, we represent them with,

$$S_{ij}(t) = 1, S_{ij} = \text{closed}$$

Conversely, when they are in the "open" state,

$$S_{ij}(t) = 0, S_{ij} = \text{open}$$

Figure 2 depicts the Transform a matrix basic architecture in images.

Fig 2: The basic structure of Matrix Converter

The matrix power converter consists of a total of 18 devices, consisting of interconnected IGBTs. Each switch, forming a block, It can conduct current in either direction depending on the gate signals, enabling versatile connections between input and output phases as needed. Notably, the matrix converter achieves variable-frequency transformation of three-phase AC line voltage without relying on DC link voltage or current.

The following conditions determine the switching state of the MC:

- (i) No two input terminals are ever shorted at the same time.
- (ii) No output terminal ever has an open circuit.

The matrix converter's AC voltages are modulated using PWM-style techniques. Modulation techniques are used to produce switching pulses for power devices. Power electronic drives frequently employ PWM control techniques. PWM enables frequency control of the voltage and current applied to the motor. PWM generates a rectangular wave with an effective value equal to the output voltage.

6.1 Matrix Converter Switching and Control:

In a three-phase matrix converter, there are 27 different switching states. The design equation for the converter and the input voltages in three phases are as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_A \\ V_B \\ V_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{in} \cos(\omega_i t) \\ V_{in} \cos(\omega_i t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ V_{in} \cos(\omega_i t - \frac{4\pi}{3}) \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

The converter's three-phase output voltages are expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_o \cos(\omega_o t) \\ V_o \cos(\omega_o t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ V_o \cos(\omega_o t - \frac{4\pi}{3}) \end{bmatrix} \tag{10}$$

Here, ω_i and ω_o represent the frequencies of the input and output voltages of the matrix converter. The three-phase output voltages of the converter can be expressed as follows:

$$M(t) = \begin{bmatrix} M_{Aa} & M_{Ab} & M_{Ac} \\ M_{Ba} & M_{Bb} & M_{Bc} \\ M_{Ca} & M_{Cb} & M_{Cc} \end{bmatrix} \tag{11}$$

The converter's transfer matrix is depicted as follows:

$$I_{in} = M^T I_o \tag{12}$$

To avoid short circuits, it is imperative to satisfy specific duty cycle requirements.

$$\begin{aligned} M_{Aa} + M_{Ba} + M_{Ca} &= 1 \\ M_{Ab} = M_{Bb} = M_{Cb} &= 1 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

$$M_{Ac} = M_{Bc} = M_{Cc} = 1$$

Duty cycles for transfer ratio are,

$$\begin{aligned} M_{Aa} &= \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta)) \\ M_{Ba} &= \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta - \frac{2\pi}{3})) \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned} M_{Ca} &= \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta - \frac{4\pi}{3})) \\ M_{Ab} &= \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta - \frac{4\pi}{3})) \\ M_{Bb} &= \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta)) \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$M_{Cb} = \frac{1}{3} (1 + 2q \cos(\omega_i t + \theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}))$$

7.1 Simulation Results

The following diagrams illustrate different parameters in relation to wind speed. Figure 6, you can observe the mechanical torque, denoted as T_m , while Figure 7 displays the generator rotor speed in radians per second (rad/s) and the generator torque, denoted as T_e .

For a wind turbine's base speed of 6 m/s, the generator's output values are as follows: $\omega_r = 151$ rad/s and $T_e = 58$ Nm. Figure 8 provides the generator rotor speed represented in revolutions per minute (rpm).

Fig 6: Mechanical Torque, T_m

Fig 7: Rotor Speed (rad/s) and Electrical Torque, T_e

Fig 8: Rotor Speed (rpm)

Fig 9 – 11 shows the line voltage of PMSG, the time taken for starting the machine initially produces no power until 0.04s. Then the power rises above the rated value and after 0.25s it reaches to the steady- state condition.

Fig 9: Line Voltage of PMSG (V_{ab})

Fig 10: Line Voltage of PMSG (V_{bc})

Fig 11: Line Voltage of PMSG (V_{ca})

Fig 12 shows the three phase output voltage and current of PMSG.

Fig 12: Three phase Output Voltage(V) and Current(A) of PMSG

The pulse width modulation (PWM) signals for the upper and lower switches in phase A are illustrated in Figure 13. The upper switch pulses exhibit a phase shift of 180 degrees relative to the lower switch pulses. Similarly, for phases B and C, pulses are generated with phase shifts of 120° and 240°, respectively

Fig 13: Sinusoidal pulse width modulation(SPWM) signals for the upper and lower switches in phase A.

Figures 14 and 15 show the three-phase voltage and three-phase current of the matrix converter. The simulation parameters are as follows: frequency = 50 Hz, output voltage = 420V, output current = 11A, resistance = 60

ohms.

Fig 14: Voltage Output from the Matrix Converter

Fig 15: Output Current of Matrix Converter

Fig 16 – 18 shows the line voltage of Matrix Converter.

Fig 16: Line Voltage of Matrix Converter (V_{ab})

Fig 17: Matrix converter's input voltage (V_{bc})

Fig 18: Line Voltage of Matrix Converter (V_{ca})

The simulated output voltage and current waveforms of the matrix converter with a filter under steady-state conditions are depicted in Figures 19 and 20.

Fig 19: Voltage Output from Matrix Converter with Three-Phase Filtering

Fig 20: Current Output from Matrix Converter with Three-Phase Filtering

8 .Conclusion

To power a variable speed wind energy conversion system that uses a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), a matrix converter will be used. The results demonstrate that the PMSG-driven wind turbine now performs more dynamically. The simulation illustrates how well the results work. The input and output voltage waveforms of the Matrix Converter show improved performance. Matrix converter-using PMSG wind turbine systems are compatible with the suggested controller. According to the simulation results, the matrix converter's input and output voltages are switching-frequency pure sine waveforms. The control circuit for creating pulses in the PWM approach is the simplest due to the designed converter's increased efficiency.

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